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SOLVENT RESIDUES IN NIFEDIPINE SOLID DISPERSION OBTAINED BY KNEADING METHOD

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Solid dispersions represent one of the most applicable approaches in increasing the solubility of poorly soluble active pharmaceutical ingredients. The kneading method is a simple method suitable in the initial stages of testing and belongs to the group of solvent-based methods for obtaining solid dispersions. Accompanied by other methods from this group, the kneading method can be limiting due to solvent residues. The aim of this study was to quantify the solvent residues in nifedipine solid dispersions with three different polymers (polyvinylpyrrolidone K 30, sodium alginate and polyethylene glycol 4000) in three different ratios, obtained using diluted ethanol by the kneading method. Physical mixtures of nifedipine and the corresponding polymers in proportions of 1:1, 1:3 and 1:5 were obtained using a powder mixer (Farmalabor, Italy). Diluted ethanol (3 ml per 1 g of physical mixture) was used as a kneading medium. The obtained pastes were dried for 24 h in an oven (Memmert, Germany) and 48 h in a desiccator, pulverized, sieved through sieve 355 and stored in a glass containers protected from light before further analyses. The ethanol content in nifedipine solid dispersions was determined on a gas chromatograph coupled to a mass spectrometer and headspace sampler (Agilent Technologies, Germany). Ethanol content above 0.5% was detected in solid dispersions with polyvinylpyrrolidone K 30 (0.75%, 1.40% and 1.47% in ratios 1:1, 1:3 and 1:5 respectively). In solid dispersions with sodium alginate, the content was much lower (about 0.003%), while in solid dispersions with polyethylene glycol 4000, the content was below the limit of detection. The content of ethanol residues in examined nifedipine solid dispersions depends on the used polymer and its proportion. Solvent residues can be a critical parameter when choosing the optimal solid dispersion formulation, especially in cases where solvents of higher toxic potential (Classes 1 or 2) would be used.

Keywords: Ethanol, Ethyl Alcohol, Solvent-Based Solid Dispersion.

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